

Analysis of Mechanical Damage Growth in Notched Carbon-Epoxy ($\pm 45^\circ$)_{ns} Laminates

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ABSTRACT

The damage growth in notched coupons of ($\pm 45^\circ$)_{2s} carbon-epoxy laminates has been analyzed in details by microscopic observation of section. Main cracks initiated by the notch grow parallel to the fiber and induce in adjacent plies small cracks. Delamination occurs by mode III crack propagation initiated by the sets of main and induced cracks. Fractographic observations are consistent with this mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

Failure in laminates composite material is the consequence of complex set of elementary events. Localized failure of the components, matrix, interface, fibers, may occur well before the complete fracture of the specimen or the structure. This damage growth with increasing applied stress is strongly dependant of the laminates structures, i.e., the orientation of each ply and the stacking sequence.

Three elementary steps of damaging take place during failure process : first ply failure occurs in 90° ply as microcracks in the matrix parallel to the fibers, shear splitting induces microcracks growth in off-axis ply, shear or normal interlaminar stress yields delamination. This schematic description of damaging process is well verified in multiply laminates system (1-2). However this mechanism need to be more precisely described, particularly for the analysis of failure process in real structures from the observation of broken part by fractography.

In this paper we present a detailed study of damage growth in a simple ($\pm 45^\circ$)_{ns} carbon-epoxy laminates. This structure is a model for the comprehension of damage growth in an angle ply laminates in which the dominant stress component is an intralaminar shear. In order to understand the different step of damage initiation and growth we have to study several states of stress and for each of them make detailed observations of microscopic failure in the material. For such purpose we have used notched sample in order to localize the damage and the

study was done by microscopic observation on polished section in the area around the crack tip. This procedure was repeated for several levels of stress in monotonic tensile test or for several steps of fatigue cycles.

EXPERIMENTAL

The composite material is made of T300 fiber and Narmco N5208 resin. The laminates are $(\pm 45^\circ)_{2s}$. Some sample were molded as $(\pm 45^\circ)_{5s}$ for tension-compression fatigue test. The dimensions of the coupons are presented on figure 1. Aluminium tabs are Epoxy bonded to the end of coupons. Monotonic tensile tests are performed on an INSTRON 1115 machine. Fatigue tests are runned on a servo-hydraulic machine MAYES ESH5. The damage growth was monitored by recording counts rate of Acoustic Emission (C.G.R). This monitoring allows us to stop the experiment at different level of damage before complete fracture.

Fig. 1 - $(\pm 45^\circ)_{2s}$ coupons

The coupons are cutted around the notch tip and small pieces of laminates embedded in resin are observed by optical microscopy. Successive sections and polishing allow us to observe the progression of damage. The scanning electron microscopy of fractographic surfaces after complete fracture are made on a CAMECA MEB 07.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The study has shown that damage growth mechanism follow a general scheme which is common for monotonic tensile test and fatigue test. Thus we shall discuss the common features of the mechanism without strict distinction between the type of loading. The fatigue experiments are more useful because, at low stress, the damage growth is very slow.

The microscopic observation of section in the crack tip area during the first stage of damage progression shows typical microcrack pattern presented on photograph 2 and figure 3. The cracks initiate at the lower corner of the

Photo 2 - Main cracks in the + 45° plies
(on left) and in the - 45° plies (on right)

Fig. 3 : Schematic drawing of microcracks in
three sections ahead of the notch tip.
Section 3 is the example shown on the Photo 2

notch tip for the + 45° plies and at the upper corner for the - 45° plies. At this stage there is only one crack parallel to the fiber in each ply. The growth of the main crack in the two outer plies (+ 45°) may be monitored during fatigue experiment. The crack growth rate is constant in a fairly long range. However, microscopic observation of section shows that there are slight differences of growth between the cracks depending of the ply. The outer plies and the + 45° plies contains larger cracks than the inner and - 45° plies.

At a further stage of damage (higher stress in a monotonic tensile test or higher number of cycle in fatigue) new set of microcracks appears beside the main cracks. The observation of section shows regular spacing like the distribution of microcrack in a 90° ply in the case of (0, ± 45, 90°) laminate (2). By observing, far from the notch, an area where there are main cracks only in the plies n°1 and 3 (photograph 4), fine cracks in the ply n°2 can be seen. These fine cracks are induced by the main cracks in the two adjacent plies. Thus each main crack induces in the adjacent plies, small cracks regularly spaced (0.1 to 0.2 mm spacing) and perpendicular to it. This pattern has been schematically drawn on figure 5 limited to three plies.

Other observation in SEM on final fracture or by observing section parallel to the plies confirm this model and show that the main cracks in the inner plies (+ or - 45°) are not single cracks but are multiple and also regularly spaced (0.1 to 0.2 mm spacing).

The next step of damaging is delamination which occurs from the crack tip and extend in the area included between the + 45° and - 45° directions. Delamination is initiated at joint of intersection of the various crack plane. Final fracture occurs when delamination has grown until the edge of the sample. This model of damage growth has been schematically divided in three steps. However, if at a given point damage occurs successively following these steps, in the whole sample the three phase of the mechanism may occur simultaneously at different place. For instance, along a main crack path, from the notch tip to the edge of the sample, one can observe at the same time, delamination, multiple crack in the main crack direction, induced cracks in adjacent plies and the growing single main crack. The study of fractographic surface by scanning electron microscopy is consistent with this model. The observation of delamination area shows the regular pattern of perpendicular cracks from one ply to another (photographs 6 and 7). A careful observation of the square surface delimited by cracks and by resin on photographs 8 and 9 reveals the radial arrangement of the resin marks (called hackle by MORRIS (3)). Details of these hackles may be observed on photograph 10.

This kind of fractographic feature may be explained by a shear failure occurring by torsion (mode III fracture mode). This torsion deformation in the laminate plane is due to the rotation of each damaged ply. Two adjacent plies, under loading, rotates in the opposite direction (4). Then, since there are regularly spaced cracks parallels to the fibers in each ply, an interlaminar shear may build up at the edge of the squares and produces shear crack propagation (mode III) from the side of the squares up to the center.

This mechanism, as shown by several SEM observation is, in the general trends, the same in monotonic and in fatigue loading. We have confirmed, by observing fractographic surface of broken ($\pm 45^\circ$)_{2S} unnotched coupons that this mechanism is also operating for the case where there are no damage localization by stress concentration (hole or notch).

Photo 4 - Induced cracks in ply n°2 . Section at 23 mm of notch tip. $[\pm 45^\circ]_{5s}$ coupon submitted to fatigue loading.

Fig. 5 - Computer schematic drawing of damage growth from a notch in $(\pm 45^\circ)_{ps}$ laminates. Drawing is limited to three plies.

0.1 mm

Photos 6 and 7

0.2 mm

squares pattern on interlaminar surface

0.1 mm

Photos 8 and 9

radial symmetry of resin marks in squares

0.05 mm

20 μ

Photo 10
Details on the "hackles" orientation

CONCLUSION

The different step of fracture process of ($\pm 45^\circ$)_{2s} laminates has been studied in details. The initiation, by a primary crack, of induced small cracks in the adjacent plies is an important result which emphasizes the role of initiation of cracks from ply to ply, in this case of intralaminar shear loading.

A peculiar fractographic pattern, radial symmetry in squares, each square being delimited by two cracks in two adjacent plies, has been explained by a mode III crack propagation. This explanation has been made possible only because the structure of damages was known by microscopic observation on section. This is a good example of the procedure for the study of fractographic significance of SEM observation. An accurate knowledge of the damaging process and cracks arrangement, together with a description of the local loading, are important conditions for the understanding of fractographic feature. These studies, which will take very long time, have to be done if we want to be able to explain fractographic observation on real broken structures and find the origin of the failure.

This work has been supported by the Délégation à la Recherche Scientifique et Technique under contract n° 79.7.0868/69.

REFERENCES

- (1) Sendeckyj, "Failure mode in composites" III A.I.M.E (1976)-Ed. Chiao, T.T., Schuster, D.M.
- (2) Reifsnider, K.L., Stinthcomb, W.W., Henneke, E.G., A.S.T.M, S.T.P 617 (1977) p 93
- (3) Morris, G.E., A.S.T.M, S.T.P. 696 (1979) p 274
- (4) Rotem, A., Hashin, Z., J. Composite Mat., Vol.9 (1975) p 191

